

Implementing usability-improved data management plans in interdisciplinary engineering projects

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NFDI4Ing Conference 2022 | October 26-27, 2022

Where did we start?

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- Two data stewards
- Active in the Cluster of Excellence "Internet of Production"
- Cluster vision: Making data available along the whole production chain
- Highly interdisciplinary environment

As data stewards...

- What are our aims?
- Meaningful RDM structures to work on?

Aims

- Raising general awareness of RDM among researchers
- Strengthening comprehensibility and reproducibility of research
- Making data available
- Creating measurable quantities
 - Types and volume of research data in the cluster
 - Degree of persistently identifiable and sustainably stored research data
- Having a DMP created by each project
- **Implementing a data management plan template/tool for the cluster**

Initial State

Vorlage Datenmanagementplan
für die RWTH Aachen University

- A lot of material on creating data management plans – for researchers
- Material lacks on implications for the work of data stewards
- Initial impressions via try-out and exchange with RDM network:
 - Practical barriers
 - Motivational/acceptance barriers
 - Variety of templates, tools
- Input by researchers needed to derive requirements

Interview Series with Researchers

Setting

- Over three months
- 28 interviews with Cluster researchers

Topics

- Types of research data
- RDM knowledge
- Perceived barriers and incentives

Methods

- Semi-structured interviews
- Predefined question flow
- Qualitative analysis via tagging in transcripts

Derived Requirements

CR1: Elaborating on relevant topics

CR2: Ensuring comprehensibility and unambiguity

OR1: Top-down structure specifications

OR2: Reducing overhead

(OR3: Integrated of further RDM functionalities)

Implementation

- Addressing cases such as business-sensitive data (CR1)
- Writing help-texts and examples for the DMP (CR2)
- Creating material/instructions for working with the DMP (CR2)
- Close coordination with and communication via cluster management (OR1)
- Fixed response options (OR2/OR3)
- Tags (OR2/OR3)
- Summarizations (OR2)
- Tool Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) (OR3)

Next Steps

- Organizational specifications with cluster management (OR1)
- DMP training for all researchers on Research Summit (CR2/OR1)
- Cluster-wide roll-out with feedback iterations (OR2)

Outlook: Linkage to further RDM services (OR3)

The screenshot shows the Coscine search interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'squirrel' and a search button. Below the search bar, there is a navigation bar with 'Home / Search'. The main content area displays search results for 'squirrel'. The first result is 'Resource: Squirrels in Europe' with the following details: Archived: false, Visibility: Public, License: CC BY 4.0 (Attribution), Alternative Title: Squirrels in Europe - S3, Conforms To: https://purl.org/coscine/ap/radar/, Subject: images, squirrel, behavior, Persistent ID: 21.11102/aa123a6f-ec5a-4e6a-bd43-4f1eb880bc77, Title: Squirrels in Europe, Description: Images of Squirrels in Europe sorted by color and size, Resource Type: RWTH-RDS-S3, and Belongs To Project: https://purl.org/coscine/projects/a2561455-625c-4aba-9f49-3d60641e8652. The second result is 'Resource: Squirrels in Serbia' with the following details: Archived: false, Visibility: Public, License: CC BY 4.0 (Attribution), Alternative Title: Squirrels in Serbia -WORM, and Conforms To: https://purl.org/coscine/ap/engmeta/. At the bottom of the search results, there is a pagination bar showing '1' and a dropdown menu for '100'.

- Tool Coscine
 - Searchable repository
 - Assignment of identifiers
 - Storage and archive
- Challenges: "Double" workload, metadata profiles, ...
- Working on possible automatic integration
- Further exploration of possible tools, functionalities, ...

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Acknowledgement

- The authors would like to thank the Federal Government and the Heads of Government of the Länder, as well as the Joint Science Conference (GWK), for their funding and support within the framework of the NFDI4Ing consortium. Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) - project number 442146713.